

A DIFFERENTIAL GAME

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Abstract. In this paper, it is considered the pursuit problem for the case when the dynamics of objects is given according to the first-order linear differential equations and their velocities are decelerating over time. Here, a parallel pursuit strategy for the pursuer is proposed and new sufficient conditions for capture are found.

Keywords: Differential game, geometrical constraint, evader, pursuer, strategy, parallel pursuit.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada obyektarning dinamikasi birinchi tartibli chiziqli differensial tenglama bo'yicha harakatlanganda va tezliklari vaqt o'tishi bilan sekinlanuvchi bo'lgan hol uchun quvish masalasi o'rganiladi. Bunda quvlovchi uchun parallel quvish strategiyasi taklif qilinadi va tutishning yangi yetarli shartlari topiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Differensial o'yin, geometrik chegaralanish, qochuvchi, quvlovchi, strategiya, parallel quvish.

Абстрактный. В статье исследуется задача преследования для случая, когда динамика объектов данное по линейному дифференциальному уравнению первого порядка и их скорости замедляются с течением времени. При этом предлагается параллельная стратегия преследования преследователя и находятся новые достаточные условия для поимки.

Ключевые слова: Дифференциальная игра, геометрическое ограничение, убегающий, преследователь, стратегия, параллельное преследование.

Let a controlled object P called the Pursuer, chase another object E called the Evader in the space \mathbb{R}^n . Denote by x a state of the Pursuer and denote by y a state of the Evader in \mathbb{R}^n . In the present we study the Pursuit problem when the objects move in accordance with equations

$$P: \dot{x} + \lambda x = u, \quad x(0) = x_0, \quad (1)$$

$$E: \dot{y} + \lambda y = v, \quad y(0) = y_0, \quad (2)$$

where $\lambda \neq 0$, $x, y, u, v \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $n \geq 2$; x_0, y_0 are the initial positions of the objects P and E , respectively; it is assumed that $x_0 \neq y_0$; the parameter u is the velocity vector of the Pursuer and here the temporal variation of u is considered to be a Lebesgue measurable function $u(\cdot): [0, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$. We denote by U_{exp}^- the set of all measurable functions $u(\cdot)$ satisfying the geometric constraint (briefly, the G_{exp}^- - constraint)

$$|u(t)| \leq \rho e^{-kt} \quad \text{for almost every } t \geq 0, \quad (3)$$

where ρ, k are positive numbers.

Similarly, the parameter v is the velocity vector of the Evader and here the temporal variation of v is considered to be a Lebesgue measurable function $v(\cdot): [0, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$. We denote by V_{exp}^- the set of all measurable functions $v(\cdot)$ such that

$$|v(t)| \leq \sigma e^{-kt} \quad \text{for almost every } t \geq 0, \quad (4)$$

where σ is a positive number.

From the physical viewpoint, the constraints (3) and (4) indicate that the maximal values of velocities of both objects will damp in duration time of the considered game.

Definition 1. The measurable function $u(\cdot) \in U_{exp}^-$ is called *the admissible control function* of the Pursuer, respectively in the game (1)–(4), or in brief, the G_{exp}^- – Game.

Definition 2. For the pair of $(x_0, u(\cdot))$, $u(\cdot) \in U_{exp}^-$ the solution of equation (1), that is, $x(t) = x_0 e^{-\lambda t} + \int_0^t e^{-\lambda(t-s)} u(s) ds$ is called *a trajectory of the Pursuer* in the interval $[0, +\infty)$.

Definition 3. For the pair of $(y_0, v(\cdot))$, $v(\cdot) \in V_{exp}^-$ the solution of equation (2), that is, $y(t) = y_0 e^{-\lambda t} + \int_0^t e^{-\lambda(t-s)} v(s) ds$ is called *a trajectory of the Evader* in the interval $[0, +\infty)$.

In the G_{exp}^- – Game, Pursuer aims to catch Evader, i.e. to realize equality $x(t) = y(t)$ for some $t > 0$, and the aim of Evader is to keep relation $x(t) \neq y(t)$ for all t , $t \geq 0$.

Let $z = x - y$, $z_0 = x_0 - y_0$. Then from (1) and (2) we have the unique equation

$$\dot{z} = u - v, \quad z(0) = z_0.$$

For decision of the Pursuit problem we are going to provide necessary conceptions and determinations.

Definition 4. A strategy $\mathbf{u}_{G_{exp}^-}(t, v)$ is called winning for Pursuer P on some time interval $[0, T]$ in the G_{exp}^- – Game if, for every $v(\cdot) \in V_{exp}^-$ there exists a moment $t^* \in [0, T]$ such that the solution $z(t)$ of the Cauchy problem

$$\dot{z} = \mathbf{u}_{G_{exp}^-}(t, v(t)) - v(t), \quad z(0) = z_0$$

is equal to zero at that moment, i.e. $z(t^*) = 0$, and this implies that $x(t^*) = y(t^*)$. Here the number T is called a guaranteed capture time.

To solve the Problem of Pursuit, assume that at each current time t , the Pursuer is allowed to know the initial states x_0, y_0 , the constants λ, ρ, σ, k , the current time t , and the value of the Evader's control $v(t)$.

Definition 5. If $\rho \geq \sigma$, then we call the function

$$\mathbf{u}_{G_{exp}^-}(t, v) = v - \lambda_{G_{exp}^-}(t, v) \xi_0 \tag{5}$$

the $\Pi_{G_{exp}^-}$ – strategy of the Pursuer in the G_{exp}^- – Game, where

$$\lambda_{G_{exp}^-}(t, v) = \langle v, \xi_0 \rangle + \sqrt{\langle v, \xi_0 \rangle^2 + \rho^2 e^{-2kt} - |v|^2},$$

$\xi_0 = z_0 / |z_0|$, and $\langle v, \xi_0 \rangle$ is a scalar product of the vectors v and ξ_0 in \mathbb{R}^n .

Property 1. If $\rho \geq \sigma$, then the function $\lambda_{G_{exp}^-}(t, v)$ is continuous, non-negative and defined for all (t, v) such that $|v| \leq \sigma e^{-kt}$ and $t \geq 0$.

Property 2. If $\rho \geq \sigma$, then the following inequality is valid for the function $\lambda_{G_{exp}^-}(t, v)$:

$$(\rho - \sigma)e^{-kt} \leq \lambda_{G_{exp}^-}(t, v) \leq (\rho + \sigma)e^{-kt}.$$

Theorem 1. a) If $\rho > \sigma$, $\lambda = k$, then the $\Pi_{G_{exp}^-}$ – strategy for Pursuer is winning on $[0, T]$, where $T = |z_0|/(\rho - \sigma)$;

b) If $\rho > \sigma$, $\lambda > k$, then the $\Pi_{G_{exp}^-}$ – strategy for Pursuer is winning on $[0, T_1]$;

c) If $\rho > \sigma$, $\lambda < k$ and $\rho - \sigma > (k - \lambda)|z_0|$, then the $\Pi_{G_{exp}^-}$ – strategy for Pursuer is winning on $[0, T_1]$, where $T_1 = \frac{1}{\lambda - k} \ln \left(1 + \frac{(\lambda - k)|z_0|}{\rho - \sigma} \right)$.

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